

Effect of Substituents on Phenol-Isocyanate Reaction

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Few reports have been published on the phenyl isocyanate-phenol reaction¹. Phenols are blocking agents for suppressing the reactivity of isocyanate at ambient temperatures². At higher temperatures (around 140°) the blocked isocyanate dissociates into phenol and the free isocyanate. The present paper deals with the evaluation of the kinetic and activation parameters for the reaction of phenyl isocyanate with some sterically hindered phenols and *ortho*- and *para*-chlorophenols.

Results and Discussion

The second order rate constants and the activation parameters for the reaction of phenyl isocyanate with phenol and substituted phenols are given in Tables 1 and 2. In the reactions catalysed by both diethylcyclohexylamine (DECHA) and dibutyltin dilaurate (DBTDL) respectively, the substituents at *ortho*-position reduced the reactivity and increased the activation energy by the steric effect. Activation energy decreased with the rate constants while the negative entropies of activation increased.

The rate constant was higher for the DBTDL catalysed reaction between 2,6-dimethylphenol and phenyl isocyanate reaction than that for the methoxyphenol-phenyl isocyanate reaction. This may be attributed to the higher nucleophilicity of the dimethylphenol. When the reaction is catalysed by diethylcyclohexylamine the higher nucleophilicity will favour the strong interaction between the tertiary amine base catalyst and the acidic phenol, and a lower rate constant is found as expected.

Usually an electron-withdrawing substituent in the phenol moiety reduces the reactivity with an isocyanate. But we observed that *p*-chlorophenol has a higher reactivity with the catalyst DECHA while the reactivity was lower when catalysed by DBTDL. This may be due to the +*m* effect in the former case when the chlorine substituent increases the electron density of the benzene ring. However with the metal catalyst, interaction of the non-bonded electron pair of the chlorine substituent with the *d*-electron orbitals of the transition metal drains the electron density on the aromatic

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR PHENOL-PHENYL ISOCYANATE REACTION CATALYSED BY DIETHYLCYCLOHEXYLAMINE (0.002 M) IN BENZENE

[Phenol]=[Phenyl isocyanate]=0.2 M

Phenol	K_a	Second order rate constant			E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		10 ³ k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				
		31°	40°	50°		
Phenol	1.1×10^{-10}	1.995	3.447	4.672	36.8	-183.28
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenol (Guaiacol)	—	0.269	0.543	1.109	59.8	-125.15
2,6-Dimethylphenol	—	0.133	0.277	0.543	63.8	-117.97
2,4-Di- <i>t</i> -butylphenol	—	0.067	0.133	0.269	67.0	-113.79
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	77	0.131	0.277	0.543	63.8	-117.79
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	6.3	2.151	3.787	5.228	34.1	-191.11

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR PHENYL ISOCYANATE-PHENOL REACTION CATALYSED BY DIBUTYLTIN DILAURATE (0.0002 M) IN BENZENE

[Phenol]=[Phenyl isocyanate]=0.2 M

Phenol	K_a	Second order rate constant			E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		10 ³ k (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				
		31°	40°	50°		
Phenol	1.1×10^{-10}	1.248	9.462	14.34	66.2	-80.93
<i>o</i> -Methoxyphenol (Guaiacol)	—	0.269	0.683	1.400	73.6	-79.17
2,6-Dimethylphenol	—	0.688	1.694	3.434	71.8	-77.35
2,4-Di- <i>t</i> -butylphenol	—	0.133	0.405	0.826	77.3	-71.67
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenol	77	0.133	0.269	0.683	76.5	-77.64
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenol	6.3	0.823	1.848	3.787	68.3	-87.81

ring. The lower reactivity of *o*-chlorophenol may be ascribed to the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bonding leading to the non-availability of the hydrogen atom for the addition reaction with the isocyanate.

The higher negative entropy of activation indicates the formation of a rigid complex in the transition state. The plots of $x/a(a-x)$ vs time gave straight lines for all the reactions, except for the reaction of 2,6-dimethylphenol (DECHA catalyst) and *p*-chlorophenol (DBTDL catalyst). The deviation from the simple second order plots may be due to the possibility of complex formation between the more acidic 2,6-dimethylphenol and the basic catalyst as also in the case of the chlorine substituent of *p*-chlorophenol with the tin atom of the catalyst.

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